
ON DIVISIBILITY OF GENERALIZED FIBONACCI NUMBERS

Miho Aoki¹

Department of Mathematics, Shimane University, Matsue, Shimane, Japan
 aoki@riko.shimane-u.ac.jp

Yuho Sakai

Department of Mathematics, Shimane University, Matsue, Shimane, Japan
 s149410@matsu.shimane-u.ac.jp

Received: 4/6/14, Revised: 2/15/15, Accepted: 4/8/15, Published: 6/5/15

Abstract

It is well-known that p divides some Fibonacci numbers F_n for any prime number p . Moreover, it is also known that any Lucas number L_n cannot be divided by 5. Let p be a prime number and $d(p)$ be the smallest positive integer n for which $p \mid F_n$. In this article, we consider the generalized Fibonacci sequence $\{G_n\}$, which satisfies the Fibonacci recurrence relation, but with arbitrary initial conditions. We define an equivalence relation among the sequences $\{G_n\}$ and give all equivalence classes $\overline{\{G_n\}}$, whose representatives $\{G_n\}$ satisfy $p \nmid G_n$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$. From the result, we know that if $p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$, then there are infinitely many generalized Fibonacci sequences $\{G_n\}$ that satisfy $p \nmid G_n$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and if $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ and $d(p) = p + 1$, then for any generalized Fibonacci sequences $\{G_n\}$, we have $p \mid G_n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

1. Introduction and Main Result

We define the *generalized Fibonacci sequence* $\{G_n\}$ by

$$G_1, G_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \quad \text{and} \quad G_{n+2} = G_{n+1} + G_n \quad \text{for any } n \geq 1.$$

Many interesting properties of the sequences are known ([2, especially see §7 and §17]). We fix a prime number p and let $d(p)$ be the order of appearance of p for the Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}$, which is defined as the smallest positive integer n such that $F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. By the periodicity modulo p ([2, §35]), we have $F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ if and only if $n \equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$. Furthermore, we know $d(p) \leq p + 1$ from the well-known properties of Fibonacci numbers.

¹This work was supported by JSPS KAKENHI Grant Numbers 26400015.

Lemma 1. ([2, §34, Theorem 34.8])

- (1) If $p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$, then we have $F_{p-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.
- (2) If $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, then we have $F_{p+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

For any integer G that is not divisible by p , we denote an inverse element modulo p by $G^{-1} (\in \mathbb{Z})$ (i.e., $GG^{-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$). Let $\{G_n\}$ and $\{G'_n\}$ be generalized Fibonacci sequences that satisfy $p \nmid G_1, G_2$ and $p \nmid G'_1, G'_2$. If $G_2G_1^{-1} \equiv G'_2G'_1{}^{-1} \pmod{p}$, then we write $\{G_n\} \sim \{G'_n\}$. This relation \sim is an equivalence relation. We denote the quotient set of this relation by

$$X_p = \{ \{G_n\} \mid \text{generalized Fibonacci sequences that satisfy } p \nmid G_1, G_2 \} / \sim .$$

By the definition of the relation \sim , each class $\overline{\{G_n\}} \in X_p$ contains infinitely many generalized Fibonacci sequences. The number of equivalence classes $\overline{\{G_n\}}$ of X_p is $|X_p| = |\mathbb{F}_p^\times| = p - 1$. Furthermore, we define the subset Y_p of X_p by

$$Y_p = \{ \overline{\{G_n\}} \in X_p \mid p \nmid G_n \text{ for any } n \in \mathbb{N} \}.$$

We know that Y_p is well-defined; the condition “ $p \nmid G_n$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ ” does not depend on a representative $\{G_n\}$ by the following lemma.

Lemma 2. Assume $p \nmid G_1, G_2, p \nmid G'_1, G'_2$, and $\{G_n\} \sim \{G'_n\}$. Then we have $p \nmid G_n$ if and only if $p \nmid G'_n$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

For any positive integers i which satisfy $i \not\equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$, let g_i ($0 \leq g_i \leq p - 1$) be the integer such that $g_i \equiv F_{i+1}F_i^{-1} \pmod{p}$. The next lemma is the key to proving our main theorem. The key lemma shows that the ratios of successive Fibonacci numbers modulo p have the period $d(p)$.

Lemma 3. Let i and j be positive integers which satisfy $i, j \not\equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$. We have $g_i = g_j$ if and only if $i \equiv j \pmod{d(p)}$.

We denote the generalized Fibonacci sequence $\{G_n\}$ such that $G_1 = a$, and $G_2 = b$ ($a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$) by $\{G(a, b)\}$. For example, $\{F_n\} = \{G(1, 1)\}$ and $\{L_n\} = \{G(1, 3)\}$. We can write $X_p = \{ \overline{\{G(1, k)\}} \mid 1 \leq k \leq p - 1 \}$. Our main theorem is as follows.

Theorem 1. (1) $Y_p = X_p - \{ \overline{\{G(1, g_i)\}} \mid 1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2 \}$.

- (2) $|Y_p| = p + 1 - d(p)$.

The next corollary immediately follows from Theorem 1, Lemma 1, and $d(5) = 5$.

Corollary 1. (1) $|Y_5| = 1$.

- (2) If $p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$, then there are infinitely many generalized Fibonacci sequences $\{G_n\}$ that satisfy $p \nmid G_n$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

(3) If $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$ and $d(p) = p + 1$, then for any generalized Fibonacci sequence $\{G_n\}$, we have $p|G_n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

If $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$, then we have $d(p) \leq p + 1$ by Lemma 1 (2). Furthermore, we get $d(p)|p + 1$ by a brief discussion (cf. [3, Lemma 2.2 (c)]). We give a necessary condition for $d(p) = p + 1$ below. We obtained the following lemma from a private discussion with Yasuhiro Kishi.

Lemma 4. *Let p be an odd prime number. If $d(p) = p + 1$, then we have $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$.*

Proof. Applying the property $F_{n+m} = F_m F_{n+1} + F_{m-1} F_n$ for $(n, m) = (\frac{p-1}{2}, \frac{p+1}{2})$ and $(n, m) = (\frac{p+1}{2}, \frac{p+3}{2})$, we get $F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2 = F_p$ and $F_{\frac{p+3}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 = F_{p+2}$. By our assumption $d(p) = p + 1$, Lemma 1, and $d(5) = 5$, we have $p \equiv \pm 2 \pmod{5}$. On the other hand, we get $F_p \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ ([1, Theorem 6]), and also $F_{p+2} \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ since $F_{p+1} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Hence we get $F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2 \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$ and $F_{\frac{p+3}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$. Furthermore, since

$$\begin{aligned} -1 \equiv F_{\frac{p+3}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 \pmod{p} &= \left(F_{\frac{p+1}{2}} + F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}\right)^2 + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 \\ &\equiv 2F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}F_{\frac{p-1}{2}} - 1 + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 \pmod{p}, \end{aligned}$$

we conclude $F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}(2F_{\frac{p-1}{2}} + F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and hence $F_{\frac{p+1}{2}} \equiv -2F_{\frac{p-1}{2}} \pmod{p}$ by our assumption that $d(p) = p + 1$. We get $-1 \equiv F_{\frac{p+1}{2}}^2 + F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2 \equiv 5F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2 \pmod{p}$. If we assume $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then we have

$$\left(\frac{5F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{5}{p}\right) = \left(\frac{p}{5}\right) = \left(\frac{\pm 2}{5}\right) = -1 \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) = 1.$$

These contradict $5F_{\frac{p-1}{2}}^2 \equiv -1 \pmod{p}$. Hence we get $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. □

The primes p which satisfy $p < 100$ and the condition $d(p) = p + 1$ are $p = 3, 7, 23, 43, 67, 83$.

2. Proofs

First, we prove Lemma 2 and Lemma 3.

Proof of Lemma 2. Let a be the integer which satisfies $a \equiv G_2 G_1^{-1} \equiv G'_2 G'_1{}^{-1} \pmod{p}$ and $1 \leq a \leq p - 1$, and $\{A_n\}$ be the generalized Fibonacci sequence defined by $A_1 = 1$ and $A_2 = a$. Then, we have $G_n \equiv A_n G_1$ and $G'_n \equiv A_n G'_1 \pmod{p}$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. As p does not divide G_1 and G'_1 , we have $p|G_n$ if and only if $p|G'_n$. \square

Proof of Lemma 3. We consider two subsequences of $F_n \pmod p$:

$$F_i, F_{i+1} \equiv g_i F_i, F_{i+2} \equiv (1 + g_i) F_i, F_{i+3} \equiv (1 + 2g_i) F_i, \dots,$$

$$F_j, F_{j+1} \equiv g_j F_j, F_{j+2} \equiv (1 + g_j) F_j, F_{j+3} \equiv (1 + 2g_j) F_j, \dots.$$

Assume $g_i = g_j$ and let k be a positive integer. Because p does not divide F_i and F_j , we have $F_{i+k} \equiv 0 \pmod p$ if and only if $F_{j+k} \equiv 0 \pmod p$. We conclude that $i + k \equiv j + k \pmod{d(p)}$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$, and obtain $i \equiv j \pmod{d(p)}$.

Conversely, we assume $i \equiv j \pmod{d(p)}$. Let $\{I_n\}$ and $\{J_n\}$ be the generalized Fibonacci sequences which are defined as $I_1 = J_1 = 1$ and $I_2 = g_i, J_2 = g_j$. We denote the above two subsequences $\pmod p$ by

$$F_i, F_{i+1} \equiv I_2 F_i, F_{i+2} \equiv I_3 F_i, F_{i+3} \equiv I_4 F_i, \dots,$$

$$F_j, F_{j+1} \equiv J_2 F_j, F_{j+2} \equiv J_3 F_j, F_{j+3} \equiv J_4 F_j, \dots.$$

By the assumption that $i \equiv j \pmod{d(p)}$, for any positive integer k , we have $i + k \equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$ if and only if $j + k \equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$. Therefore, we have $F_{i+k} \equiv 0 \pmod p$ if and only if $F_{j+k} \equiv 0 \pmod p$. Since p does not divide F_i and F_j , we get $I_{k+1} \equiv 0 \pmod p$ if and only if $J_{k+1} \equiv 0 \pmod p$. By the formulas

$$I_{k+1} = F_{k-1} I_1 + F_k I_2 = F_{k-1} + F_k g_i \quad \text{and} \quad J_{k+1} = F_{k-1} J_1 + F_k J_2 = F_{k-1} + F_k g_j,$$

we have $F_k g_i \equiv F_k g_j \pmod p$. Since $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$ by $i, j \not\equiv 0 \pmod{d(p)}$, we have $g_i \equiv g_j \pmod p$. Furthermore, since $0 \leq g_i, g_j \leq p - 1$, we get $g_i = g_j$. \square

Proposition 1. *Assume $p \nmid G_1, G_2$. For all positive integers n which satisfy $n \not\equiv 2 \pmod{d(p)}$, we have $p | G_n$ if and only if $-G_1 G_2^{-1} \equiv g_{n-2} \pmod p$.*

Proof. This follows from the well-known formula $G_n = F_{n-2} G_1 + F_{n-1} G_2$. \square

Proposition 2. *Assume $p \nmid G_1, G_2$. We have $p | G_n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ if and only if $-G_1 G_2^{-1} \equiv g_i \pmod p$ for some i which satisfies $1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2$.*

Proof. If $n \equiv 2 \pmod{d(p)}$, then we have $G_n = F_{n-2} G_1 + F_{n-1} G_2 \equiv F_{n-1} G_2 \not\equiv 0 \pmod p$. Furthermore, if $i = d(p) - 1$, then we have $-G_1 G_2^{-1} \not\equiv g_i \pmod p$ as we have assumed $p \nmid G_1$ and $g_{d(p)-1} \equiv F_{d(p)} F_{d(p)-1}^{-1} \equiv 0 \pmod p$. Hence it suffices to show that we have $p | G_n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$ which satisfies $n \not\equiv 2 \pmod{d(p)}$ if and only if $-G_1 G_2^{-1} \equiv g_i \pmod p$ for some i which satisfies $1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 1$. This follows from Proposition 1 and Lemma 3. \square

Next, we prove the main theorem.

Proof of Theorem 1. (1) Since the Fibonacci numbers satisfy $F_{n+m} = F_m F_{n+1} + F_{m-1} F_n$, we have $0 \equiv F_{d(p)} = F_{i+(d(p)-i)} = F_{d(p)-i} F_{i+1} + F_{d(p)-i-1} F_i \pmod{p}$ for any i ($1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2$). Therefore, $g_i \equiv -g_{d(p)-i-1}^{-1} \pmod{p}$. By Lemma 3 and Proposition 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} Y_p &= X_p - \{\overline{\{G_n\}} \in X_p \mid p \mid G_n \text{ for some } n \in \mathbb{N}\} \\ &= X_p - \{\overline{\{G(1, k)\}} \mid 1 \leq k \leq p - 1, -k^{-1} \equiv g_i \pmod{p} \\ &\hspace{15em} \text{for some } i (1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2)\} \\ &= X_p - \{\overline{\{G(1, k)\}} \mid 1 \leq k \leq p - 1, -k^{-1} \equiv g_{d(p)-i-1} \pmod{p} \\ &\hspace{15em} \text{for some } i (1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2)\} \\ &= X_p - \{\overline{\{G(1, k)\}} \mid 1 \leq k \leq p - 1, k \equiv -g_{d(p)-i-1}^{-1} \pmod{p} \\ &\hspace{15em} \text{for some } i (1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2)\} \\ &= X_p - \{\overline{\{G(1, g_i)\}} \mid 1 \leq i \leq d(p) - 2\}. \end{aligned}$$

(2) By Lemma 3, we know $g_i \neq g_j$ if $1 \leq i, j \leq d(p) - 2$ and $i \neq j$. Hence we conclude $|Y_p| = |X_p| - (d(p) - 2) = (p - 1) - (d(p) - 2) = p + 1 - d(p)$. \square

3. Examples

p	$d(p)$	Y_p
3	4	\emptyset
5	5	$\overline{\{L_n\}} (= \overline{\{G(1, 3)\}})$
7	8	\emptyset
11	10	$\overline{\{G(1, 4)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 8)\}}$
13	7	$\overline{\{G(1, 3)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 4)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 5)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 7)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 9)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 10)\}},$ $\overline{\{G(1, 11)\}}$
17	9	$\overline{\{G(1, 3)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 4)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 6)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 7)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 9)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 11)\}},$ $\overline{\{G(1, 12)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 14)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 15)\}}$
19	18	$\overline{\{G(1, 5)\}}, \overline{\{G(1, 15)\}}$

Table 1. Y_p for small prime numbers p

Acknowledgments The authors would like to express their gratitude to the referee and the editor for their valuable comments and suggestions. We added Lemma 4 by referee's suggestion. We also want to thank Y. Kishi for telling us the proof of Lemma 4.

References

- [1] V. E., Jr. Hoggatt and M. Bicknell, Some congruences of the Fibonacci numbers modulo a prime p , *Math. Mag.* 47, 210–214 (1974).
- [2] T. Koshy, *Fibonacci and Lucas numbers with applications*, Pure and Applied Mathematics, New York (2001).
- [3] D. Marques, The order of appearance of integers at most one away from Fibonacci numbers, *Fibonacci Quart.* 50, no.1, 36–43(2012).